

List of contributing authors from diverse communities of knowledge

This list includes all the invited potential and confirmed contributing authors:

Potential contributing authors' names	Accepted to contribute and sent contribution	Country-ies of affiliation	Country-ies of citizenship	Disciplines and expertise
Forrest Becker	Yes	United States of America	United States of America	Indigenous and local knowledge
Felipe Vander Velden	Yes	Brazil	Brazil	Anthropology, Indigenous and local knowledge
Kamal Rai	Yes	Nepal	Nepal	Resource conservation, Indigenous and local knowledge
Ana Ladio	Yes	Argentina	Argentina	Ethnobiologist (Ethnobotany), Resources conservation, Indigenous and local knowledge
Celeste Medrano	No	Argentina		Biology/anthropology, Indigenous ontologies
Gabriel Ricardo Nemogá Soto	No	Canada		Indigenous and local knowledge
Tina Ngata	No	New Zealand		Indigenous and local knowledge
Ulysses Paulino Albuquerque	No	Brazil	Brazil	Ethnobiologist (Ethnozoology) Resources conservation Indigenous and local knowledge
Laura DeLuca	Yes	United States of America		Conservation Anthropology Community conservation in Northern Tanzania. Indigenous and local knowledge Wildlife conservation in East Africa.
Ewa Domańska	No	Poland	Poland	History, environmental humanities
Kimberly Christen	No	United States of America		Anthropology Digital technologies Heritage, Intellectual property systems Indigenous and local knowledge Expertise in Australia.
Florian Kaiser	No	Germany		Social psychology, Sustainability
Wes Schultz	No	United States of America		Social Psychology, Behavior change
Kristian Nielsen	Yes	Denmark	Denmark	Social psychology / behaviour change, Biodiversity, Transformation, Climate
Maja Göpel	No	Germany	Germany	Inner Transformations, Economy
Cass R. Sunstein	No	United States of America		Behavioral Economics and Public Policy
Jayden Rae	No	The Decision Lab		Public policy, behavioral change
Elizabeth Shove	No	United Kingdom of Great Britain		Sociology, Consumption, Everyday practice

		and Northern Ireland		
Yoshihisa Kashima	Yes	Australia	Japan	Cultural Psychology
Lorraine Whitmarsh	No	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland		Environmental Psychology
Takahiro Kubo	No	Japan	Japan	Behavioral economics
Kotoko Yadomaru	Yes	Japan	Japan	Behavior change, Youth movement
Javier Taks	No	Uruguay		Environmental anthropology, Human environmental interactions
Lucia Reisch	No	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland		Behavioral economics and policy
Francisco Alpizar	Yes	Netherlands [Kingdom of the]	Costa Rica	Behavioural economics
José D. Lopez-Rivas	Yes	Netherlands [Kingdom of the]	Colombia	Behavioural economics
Michelle McCauley	No	United States of America		Conservation Psychology
Vanessa Reid	No	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland		Artist, activist, Spiritual ecologist
Rachelle Gould	Yes	United States of America	United States of America	Reviewed behavioral theories for the IPBES Values Assessment as a lead author, Environmental sociology and education, Cultural ecosystem services
Sian Sullivan	Yes	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland	Namibia, United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland	Political ecology
Harriet Bulkeley	No	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland		Environmental politics/Governance
Leonardo van den Berg	Yes	Netherlands [kingdom of the]	Brazil, Netherlands [kingdom of the]	Agroecology and social movements
Yevgeniy Bluwstein	Yes	Switzerland	Germany	Political ecology, geography
Lyla Mehta	Yes	Austria	India, Norway,	Development, environment and gender

			United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland	
Ciara Kierens	No	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland		Social anthropology, Political ecology, Public health
Eduardo Gudynas	No	Uruguay	Uruguay	Political ecology, Extractivism
Maria Mancilla Garcia	Yes	Belgium, Sweden	Spain	Environmental /Water management, Epistemology
Andy Stirling	Yes	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland	Non-governmental organizations, activism
Amaranta Herrero	Yes	Spain	Spain	Environmental sociology, Ecological justice, Multi-species perspectives, Local government, Food-system transformation
Angela Moriggi	Yes	Italy	Italy	Sustainability social science, Care and feminist approaches to transformative change
Emily Jones	Yes	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland		International law & gender, environment, Posthumanism
Luigi Pellizzoni	Yes	Italy	Italy	Sociology, social theory & Environmental politics
Flor Avelino	No	Netherlands [Kingdom of the]		Transitions, Sustainability, Power
Anna Birney	No	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland		Systems practice, Sustainability
Jamila Haider	Yes	Sweden	Austria, Canada	Socioeconomic status Social ecological systems
Glenn Denning	No	United States of America		Development practice and transformative change, Systems practice and policy, Food & agricultural systems
Alex Awiti	Yes	Kenya	Kenya	Social-ecological interactions & politics, Resilience, Environmental sciences
Jyotsna Puri	Yes	Italy; India	India	Socio-Economics, Environmental policy and change, Monitoring & Evaluation, Transformation & adaptation
Ruth DeFries	No	United States of America		Ecology, geography and sustainable development

Iago Otero	Yes	Switzerland	Spain	Spirituality, Transformative change
Yoko Lu	Yes	International	Canada	Intergenerational equity and justice in transformative changes
Polina Blinova	Yes	Switzerland	Russia, Switzerland	Youth organization, Biodiversity
Christoph Woiwode	Yes	Germany	Germany, India	Spirituality
Sam Buckton	Yes	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland	Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning
Rachel Bathurst	Yes	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland	Sustainability and theology
Tilman Hertz	Yes	Sweden	Germany	Social ecological systems Philosophy of science
Aubrey Makuleke	No	South Africa	South Africa	Protected areas, Resource conservation, Education, Community management
Fanie Phandavhudzi	No	South Africa	South Africa	Protected areas, Resource conservation, Education, Community management
Thomas Meque	No	Mozambique	Mozambique	Protected areas, Resource conservation, Education, Community management
Aniek Hebinck	Yes	Netherlands [Kingdom of the]		Social-ecological transitions
David Ludwig	Yes	Netherlands [Kingdom of the]	Germany	Philosophy of Science, Non-western epistemologies
Simon West	Yes	Sweden	Australia	Sustainability science
Arturo Escobar	No	United States of America	Colombia	Anthropology (political ontology, decolonization)